

PRINCIPLES OF DIGITAL DIDACTICS IN THE FORMATION OF ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP COMPETENCY

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Abstract. *The article reveals the principles on the basis of which the transformation of pedagogical didactics into the digital aspect should be carried out, taking into account the implementation of educational work on the formation of moral competencies in students; the features of the development of active citizenship competence in the context of digital didactics are considered, their advantages and disadvantages are substantiated, and proposals are given for minimizing the negative impact of the digital environment to create conditions for the formation of citizenship.*

Keywords: *school, lesson, citizenship, competencies, digital pedagogy, didactics, innovation*

Аннотация. *В статье раскрываются принципы, на основе которых следует поводить трансформацию педагогической дидактики в цифровой аспект с учётом проведения воспитательной работы по формированию нравственных компетенций у учащихся; рассматриваются особенности развития компетенции активной гражданственности в срезе цифровой дидактики, обосновываются их преимущества и недостатки, даны предложения минимизирования негативного влияния цифровой среды для создания условий формирования гражданственности.*

Ключевые слова: *школа, урок, гражданственность, компетенции, цифровая педагогика, дидактика, инновации*
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Annotatsiya. *Maqolada pedagogik didaktikani raqamli jihatga o‘tkazish o‘quvchilarda axloqiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish bo‘yicha tarbiyaviy ishlarni amalga oshirishni hisobga olgan holda amalga oshirilishi lozim bo‘lgan tamoyillar ochib berilgan; raqamli didaktika kontekstida faol fuqarolik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish xususiyatlari ko‘rib chiqilib, ularning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari asoslab berilgan, fuqarolikni shakllantirish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratish uchun raqamli muhitning salbiy ta‘sirini minimallashtirish bo‘yicha takliflar berilgan.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *maktab, dars, fuqarolik, kompetensiyalar, raqamli pedagogika, didaktika, innovatsiya*

The current state of pedagogical didactics is increasingly acquiring a digital appearance. At the same time, digital features in pedagogy transform the entire holistic educational system into an innovative environment: goals, means, forms, methods and technologies, conditions and factors of an effective educational process are subject to change [1,2].

However, it should be understood that digital didactics is only a learning environment; with its dominance, the role of participants in the educational process changes, where there is an initial sharp increase in interest in learning, and subsequently these indicators gradually decrease, affecting motivation. That is why the implementation of digital learning should be guided by certain principles that allow minimizing motivational, psychological, pedagogical, and methodological losses.

From the point of view of developing moral competencies, digital didactics also needs to define some fundamental principles. Let us consider in particular the process of formation of such

a moral component as the competence of active citizenship. With direct interaction between participants in the educational process, citizenship as a social and personal quality of a student is formed under the influence of several direct factors:

a) study of subjects of the humanitarian cycle, moral education, one of the objects of which is the development of moral competencies, including citizenship;

b) extracurricular work, which involves systematically engaging in organizational activities that reveal the essence of the cultural values of a given area (trips to exhibitions, theaters, cinema, museums, participation in competitions, staging plays, holding poetry evenings, organizing national holidays, etc.)

c) interaction of social institutions with the school (makhalla, family, higher education institutions, professional organizations, etc.)

d) integrated lessons with a clearly defined educational goal (through exposing numbers to national color, through texts of a local history nature, through local natural objects, etc.)

When these factors are transformed into digital didactics, the technological aspect changes, implying high-speed learning for students. Meanwhile, it should be understood that education depends on some direct conditions, in particular, the time component. If it is possible to teach, introduce a topic, teach with modern technologies in a short period of time, then it is not possible to bring up in one lesson. This is also proven by the fact that key competencies are difficult to measure: it is possible to diagnose knowledge, skills and abilities using mobile innovative means, but it is impossible to diagnose the level of competence of active citizenship through digital one-time provision [3]. For this purpose, there is a separate set of research methods, among which test diagnostics is far from the first place.

From this point of view, digital didactics should be considered not as a complete “digitized” pedagogical unit, but only as an element of innovative pedagogy that transforms technological problems into a new solution. Based on this, one of the most important principles of digital didactics in the process of formation of citizenship is its interaction with traditional didactics, not its complete replacement, integration of existing methods with technological approaches.

The second as well important principle of digital didactics in instilling a sense of citizenship is the principle of security. With free access to information systems, first of all, students need to develop divergent competencies that allow them to discard unnecessary, harmful information. These skills also develop under conditions of prolonged information exposure.

Programs created in the digital field must be suitable for the topic of the lesson, satisfy the goals and objectives of the lesson, additional material must be indirect in nature and not attract more attention than the topic itself. In other words, the technical component must be clearly adapted to the topic.

Digital didactics opens up the possibility of working with multi-level objects: inclusive education, working with talented students. Taking this feature into account, the material should be prepared individually. This will make it possible to test a larger number of respondents, as well as motivate the majority of students to do additional work. An individual approach implies the mobility of a digital system.

Projecting a pedagogical request is the most problematic aspect of digital didactics. Two subjects creating digital models (a teacher and a programmer) must take into account the interests and capabilities of professional tasks. For an IT product to be truly useful, both professionals must work in tandem.

Thus, summing up the above, it can be argued that digital didactics should be guided by the following basic principles:

The principle of Integrativeness

The principle of safety

The principle of adaptability

The principle of mobility

The principle of projecting

It is especially important to be based on these principles if an educational task is set. Education of moral qualities, including citizenship, is a labor-intensive and lengthy process. The formation of these competencies in the lesson process has a number of advantages, including those aimed at resource-saving technologies. That is why the role of digital didactics in this process cannot be underestimated. With timely and accurate access to digital technologies, as well as with its integration into traditional didactics, it is possible to obtain a worthy result in cultivating a harmoniously developed personality of the 21st century.

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